

A Similarity Measure for Clustering and its Applications

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Abstract—This paper introduces a measure of similarity between two clusterings of the same dataset produced by two different algorithms, or even the same algorithm (K-means, for instance, with different initializations usually produce different results in clustering the same dataset). We then apply the measure to calculate the similarity between pairs of clusterings, with special interest directed at comparing the similarity between various machine clusterings and human clustering of datasets. The similarity measure thus can be used to identify the best (in terms of most similar to human) clustering algorithm for a specific problem at hand. Experimental results pertaining to the text categorization problem of a Portuguese corpus (wherein a translation-into-English approach is used) are presented, as well as results on the well-known benchmark IRIS dataset. The significance and other potential applications of the proposed measure are discussed.

Keywords—Clustering Algorithms, Clustering Applications, Similarity Measures, Text Clustering.

I. INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

OUR study of similarity of clustering was initially motivated by a research on automated text categorization of foreign language texts, as explained below.

As the amount of digital documents has been increasing dramatically over the years as the Internet grows, information management, search, and retrieval, etc., have become practically important problems.

Developing methods to organize large amounts of unstructured text documents into a smaller number of meaningful clusters would be very helpful as document clustering is vital to such tasks as indexing, filtering, automated metadata generation, word sense disambiguation, population of hierarchical catalogues of web resources and, in general, any application requiring document organization [1], [2]. Document clustering is also useful for topics such as Gene Ontology [3] in biomedicine where hierarchical catalogues are needed.

To deal with the large amounts of data, machine learning

approaches have been applied to perform Automated Text Clustering (ATC). Given an unlabeled dataset, this ATC system builds clusters of documents that are hopefully similar to clustering (classification, categorization, or labeling) performed by human experts.

To identify a suitable tool and algorithm for clustering that produces the best clustering solutions, it becomes necessary to have a method for comparing the results of different clustering algorithms. Though considerable work has been done in designing clustering algorithms, not much research has been done on formulating a measure for the similarity of two different clustering algorithms.

Thus, the main goal of this paper is to: First, propose an algorithm for performing similarity analysis among different clustering algorithms; second, apply the algorithm to calculate similarity of various pairs of clustering methods applied to a Portuguese corpus and the Iris dataset; finally, to cross-validate the results of similarity analysis with the Euclidean (centroids) distances and Pearson correlation coefficient, using the same datasets. Possible applications are discussed.

II. CLUSTERING METHODS

A cluster is a collection of objects which are ‘similar’ between them and are ‘dissimilar’ to the objects belonging to other clusters [4]; and a clustering algorithm aims to find a natural structure or relationship in an unlabeled data set.

There are several categories of clustering algorithms. In this paper we will be focusing on algorithms that are exclusive in that the clusters may not overlap.

Some of the algorithms are hierarchical and probabilistic. A hierarchical algorithm clustering algorithm is based on the union between the two nearest clusters. The beginning condition is realized by setting every datum as a cluster. After a few iterations, it reaches the final clusters wanted. The final category of probabilistic algorithms is focused around model matching using probabilities as opposed to distances to decide clusters. EM or Expectation Maximization is an example of this type of clustering algorithm.

In [5], Pen et al. utilized cluster analysis composed of 2 methods. In Method I, a majority voting committee with 3 results generates the final analysis result. The performance measure of the classification is decided by majority vote of the committee. If more than 2 of the committee members give the same classification result, then the clustering analysis for that observation is successful; otherwise, the analysis fails.

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Kalton et al. [6] did clustering and after letting the algorithm create its own clusters, added a step. After the clustering was completed each member of a class was assigned the value of the cluster's majority population. The authors noted that the approach loses detail, but allowed them to evaluate each clustering algorithm against the "correct" clusters.

III. THE SIMILARITY MEASURE ALGORITHM

To measure the 'similarity' of two sets of clusters, we define a simple formula here: Let $C = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_m\}$ and $D = \{D_1, D_2, \dots, D_n\}$ be the results of two clustering algorithms on the same data set. Assume C and D are "hard" or exclusive clustering algorithms where clusters produced are pair-wise disjoint, i.e., each pattern from the dataset belongs to exactly one cluster. Then the similarity matrix for C and D is an $m \times n$ matrix $S_{C,D}(1)$.

$$S_{C,D} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & \dots & S_{1j} & \dots & S_{1n} \\ & & & \dots & & \\ S_{i1} & S_{i2} & \dots & S_{ij} & \dots & S_{in} \\ & & & \dots & & \\ S_{m1} & S_{m2} & \dots & S_{mj} & \dots & S_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $S_{ij} = p/q$, which is Jaccard's Similarity Coefficient [7] with p being the size of intersection and q being the size of the union of cluster sets C_i and D_j . The similarity of clustering C and clustering D is then defined as

$$\text{Sim}(C, D) = \sum_{i \leq m, j \leq n} S_{ij} / \max(m, n) \quad (2)$$

For Example 1, let $C_1 = \{1,2,3,4\}$, $C_2 = \{5,6,7,8\}$ and $D_1 = \{1,2\}$, $D_2 = \{3,4\}$, $D_3 = \{5,6\}$, $D_4 = \{7,8\}$ thus $m=4$ and $n=2$, then the similarity between clustering C and D is given by the following matrix $S_{C,D}$.

TABLE I
SIMILARITY MATRIX ON EXAMPLE 1 DATA

Cluster	D ₁	D ₂	D ₃	D ₄
C ₁	2/4	2/4	0/6	0/6
C ₂	0/6	0/6	2/4	2/4

In cell C_1D_1 , $p=|C_1 \cap D_1|=|\{1,2\}|=2$, and $q=|C_1 \cup D_1|=|\{1,2,3,4\}|=4$. Therefore, cell $C_1D_1=p/q=2/4$. Similarly the other cells of the matrix are calculated. Thus, the similarity between cluster set C and cluster set D in this case is $\text{Sim}(C, D) = (2/4+2/4+0/6+0/6+0/6+0/6+2/4+2/4)/4 = 0.5$

For Example 2, let $C_1 = \{1,2,3,4,5,6\}$, $C_2 = \{7,8\}$; $D_1 = \{1,2,3,4\}$, $D_2 = \{5,6,7,8\}$, thus $m=2$, $n=2$ and matrix $S_{C,D}$ is:

TABLE II
SIMILARITY MATRIX ON EXAMPLE 2 DATA

Cluster	D ₁	D ₂
C ₁	4/6	2/8
C ₂	0/6	2/4

Thus, the similarity $\text{Sim}(C, D)$, according to the similarity matrix above, is $(4/6+2/8+0/6+2/4)/2 = 17/24$ or 0.7083

It is easy to show that $0 < \text{Sim}(C, D) \leq 1$; and $\text{Sim}(C, D)=1$ for two identical clustering, where the similarity matrix $\text{Sim}(C, D)$ is a square matrix; and that this measure is only applicable to clustering a finite set of patterns into a finite number of disjoint (or non-overlapping) clusters.

Also, we can take the square of summation of the matrix values to define similarity $\text{Sim}(C, D)$, i.e., let $\text{Sim}(C, D) = (\sum_{ij} S_{ij} / \max(m, n))^2$, this would have the effect of giving a lower value of similarity but without changing its range of (0, 1]. This similarity measure is a reasonable one to use because, if we define the dissimilarity or "distance" between two clusterings C and D as $U(C,D) = 1 - \text{Sim}(C,D)$, then it can be proved that $U(C,D)$ is a good distance measure for it satisfies all desirable properties (non-negativity, identity, symmetry, triangle inequality) of a distance metric.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Fig. 1 illustrates the steps carried out for similarity measure of clustering a Portuguese corpus. The details of the "translation based text categorization" technique for foreign-language texts are found in [8] and briefly described below. (The Iris dataset that is used in our second set of experiments does not require any preprocessing.)

Fig. 1 Methodology for calculating similarity measure of clustering the Portuguese dataset

A. The Datasets

The Portuguese CETEMPublico corpus consisting of 1.5 million extracts, more than 225 million tokens, is excerpts of Portuguese newspaper Publico [9]. There are total of 9 different categories which are shown in Table III. The "nd" category which is short for "not defined" was excluded from our experiments. 1000 randomly chosen documents with at least 75 tokens were extracted for each category and then translated into English using the Google translation service [10].

Iris dataset, one of the most popular datasets in pattern recognition literature, was used as benchmark dataset. The dataset can be downloaded from Machine Learning Repository at University of California, Irvine [11]. The dataset is summarized in Table IV.

TABLE III
 GENRES COVERED IN THE CETEMPUBLICO CORPUS

ID	Category	Description	Samples
1	clt	Culture	1000
2	clt-soc	Culture-Society	1000
3	com	Technology	1000
4	des	Sports	1000
5	eco	Economics	1000
6	opi	Opinions	1000
7	pol	Politics	1000
8	soc	Society	1000
Total:			8000

TABLE IV
 IRIS DATASET

ID	Category	Samples
1	Iris Setosa	50
2	Iris Versicolour	50
3	Iris Virginica	50
Total		150

B. Preprocessing Portuguese Dataset

Tokenization was carried out by using suitable delimiters such as white-space and punctuation marks. Stop words or functional words such as article, prepositions, etc. that are not useful in the text categorization process were removed during preprocessing. Stemming was used to extract the root form of each word in the document. Since stem word as features performs better than single words and noun-phrase [12], we applied the popular and publicly available Porter Stemmer algorithm to stem translated English words [13].

Though there are various term weighting schemes such as BINARY, TF, LOGTF, LOGTFIDF, IDF, TF-CHI, TF-RF [14], [15], we used the traditional but popular weighting scheme, TF.IDF which is one of the best performance wise.

C. Clustering Algorithms

In experimenting with our clustering similarity algorithm the following clustering algorithms were studied:

- A. Repeated Bisection
- B. Direct
- C. Agglomerative
- D. Graph
- E. K-means
- F. K-medoids
- G. EM

For the first four algorithms (A - D), gCLUTO [16], a cross-platform graphical application for clustering low- and high-dimensional datasets and for analyzing the characteristics of the various clusters, was used. gCLUTO is built on top of the CLUTO clustering library.

For K-means (E) and K-medians (F) the Matlab Fuzzy Clustering and Data Analysis Toolbox [17] was utilized.

Finally, for Expectation Maximization (G) the WEKA (Waikato Environment for Knowledge Analysis) [18] tool was used.

D. Clustering Similarity Analysis

After applying the clustering algorithms on Portuguese and Iris datasets, clustering similarities were calculated using the

proposed algorithm. The results were then verified by calculating centroid Euclidean distance and Pearson correlation.

Euclidean distance:

$$d = \sqrt{\sum (X - Y)^2} \quad (3)$$

Pearson correlation coefficient:

$$r = \frac{\sum XY - \frac{\sum X \sum Y}{N}}{\sqrt{\left(\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N} \right) \left(\sum Y^2 - \frac{(\sum Y)^2}{N} \right)}} \quad (4)$$

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Pair-wise similarity matrix for all the clustering algorithms mentioned in section IV.C and with the human-labeled actual categories (H) was generated using the Similarity Algorithm we've proposed and cross verified with results from Euclidean distance and Pearson correlation.

Due to space limitation only the final similarity matrix between Repeated Bisection and the rest of the algorithms including human-labeled actual categories are shown and cluster is abbreviated as (Cl.) in the result tables. The significant values in the result tables have been **emphasized**: value closest to 1 in similarity matrix, smallest value for Euclidian distance i.e. smallest distance between cluster centroids, and closest value to +1 for Pearson correlation i.e. best positive relationship between centroids.

A summary of the similarity among A, B, C, D, and H on the Portuguese Dataset is as shown in Table V. Algorithms E, F, and G were not applied to Portuguese dataset due to their implementation limitation as they ran out of memory on a machine with 4 GB RAM. Repeated Bisection and Agglomerative gave 78% (highest) similar clusters. Repeated Bisection was also most similar to Human-labeled actual categories with 66% similarity compared to the rest of the algorithms.

TABLE V
 FINAL SIMILARITY AMONG A, B, C, D, AND H ON PORTUGUESE CORPUS

Algorithms	A	B	C	D	H
A	1	0.6634	0.7813	0.5963	0.6634
B	0.6634	1	0.6009	0.5812	0.5967
C	0.7813	0.6009	1	0.5919	0.6511
D	0.5963	0.5812	0.5919	1	0.5856

The similarity among all 7 (A - G) algorithms and actual categories on Iris dataset is shown in Table VI. Repeated Bisection and Direct algorithms resulted 100% similar clusters while they both gave clusters 95% similar to actual categories. As expected K-means and K-medoids resulted 90% similar clusters, but resulted the clusters that are least similar to human-labeled actual categories.

A. Repeated Bisection (A) vs. Human Categorization (H)

1) Results on Portuguese Dataset

A₀ - A₇ are clusters given by Repeated Bisection Algorithm and H₀ - H₇ are human-labeled actual categories. The Sim(A, H) is 0.6634.

TABLE VII
SIMILARITY MATRIX BETWEEN A AND H

Cl.	H ₀ soc	H ₁ eco	H ₂ clt-soc	H ₃ des	H ₄ pol	H ₅ clt	H ₆ com	H ₇ opi
A ₀	0.0358	0.5544	0.0310	0.0104	0.0229	0.0192	0.0514	0.0305
A ₁	0.0100	0.0110	0.0991	0.0025	0.0030	0.0136	0.5737	0.0100
A ₂	0.0987	0.0088	0.1123	0.0056	0.0139	0.0315	0.0197	0.1217
A ₃	0.0105	0.0033	0.0110	0.7675	0.0043	0.0129	0.0361	0.0183
A ₄	0.0379	0.0258	0.0105	0.0048	0.5387	0.0177	0.0013	0.1372
A ₅	0.2781	0.0481	0.0539	0.0058	0.0245	0.0235	0.0043	0.1779
A ₆	0.0472	0.0037	0.3282	0.0062	0.0150	0.0444	0.0100	0.0150
A ₇	0.0639	0.0010	0.0173	0.0045	0.0163	0.5353	0.0116	0.0433

TABLE VIII
CENTROID EUCLIDIAN DISTANCE BETWEEN A AND H

Cl.	H ₀	H ₁	H ₂	H ₃	H ₄	H ₅	H ₆	H ₇
A ₀	0.0435	0.0400	0.0408	0.0502	0.0128	0.0423	0.0440	0.0398
A ₁	0.0406	0.0336	0.0108	0.0498	0.0461	0.0418	0.0455	0.0395
A ₂	0.0405	0.0335	0.0472	0.0503	0.0504	0.0341	0.0438	0.0342
A ₃	0.0405	0.0423	0.0460	0.0069	0.0498	0.0419	0.0437	0.0398
A ₄	0.0360	0.0367	0.0443	0.0440	0.0428	0.0273	0.0113	0.0309
A ₅	0.0327	0.0292	0.0397	0.0429	0.0395	0.0239	0.0321	0.0170
A ₆	0.0349	0.0205	0.0427	0.0473	0.0474	0.0390	0.0413	0.0333
A ₇	0.0109	0.0328	0.0417	0.0432	0.0467	0.0341	0.0385	0.0312

TABLE IX
PEARSON CORRELATION BETWEEN A AND H

Cl.	H ₀	H ₁	H ₂	H ₃	H ₄	H ₅	H ₆	H ₇
C ₀	0.4199	0.5278	0.5595	0.3436	0.9593	0.4722	0.4487	0.5171
C ₁	0.4533	0.6422	0.9672	0.3128	0.4502	0.4416	0.3643	0.4783
C ₂	0.4753	0.6583	0.3864	0.3172	0.3585	0.6476	0.4271	0.6333
C ₃	0.4254	0.3940	0.3790	0.9864	0.3372	0.4133	0.3856	0.4409
C ₄	0.4843	0.4882	0.3716	0.3938	0.4738	0.7206	0.9543	0.6168
C ₅	0.5540	0.6611	0.4793	0.4057	0.5438	0.7754	0.6166	0.8795
C ₆	0.5399	0.8505	0.4339	0.3208	0.3691	0.4520	0.4144	0.5766
C ₇	0.9479	0.5524	0.4062	0.3782	0.3326	0.5237	0.4279	0.5685

2) Results on Iris Dataset

Repeated Bisection (A) did show a slight deviation from a perfect match to human categorization. Clusters A₁ and H₂ showed a distance of 0.1073 and A₂ and H₁ 0.0643. Clusters centroid A₀ showed a perfect match with the human labeled centroid H₀. The similarity values of the Pearson correlation coefficient support this as they range from 0.99992-1. This supports the 95% similarity result obtained from our similarity algorithm.

TABLE VI
FINAL SIMILARITY AMONG A - G CLUSTERING ALGORITHMS ON IRIS DATASET

Toolbox Clustering Algorithm	gCLUTO				Matlab Fuzzy-clustering toolbox		Weka EM	Actual
	Repeated Bisection	Direct	Agglomerative	Graph	K-Means	K-Medoid		
Repeated Bisection	1	1	0.93603	0.74252	0.67408	0.66896	0.84922	0.95303
Direct	1	1	0.93603	0.74252	0.67408	0.66896	0.84922	0.95303
Agglomerative	0.93603	0.93603	1	0.72289	0.67092	0.66682	0.86789	0.94505
Graph	0.74252	0.74252	0.72289	1	0.50520	0.66682	0.67306	0.72250
K-Means	0.67408	0.67408	0.67092	0.50520	1	0.90343	0.66639	0.67178
K-Medoid	0.66896	0.66896	0.66682	0.66682	0.90343	1	0.66370	0.66740
EM	0.84922	0.84922	0.86789	0.67306	0.66639	0.66370	1	0.88041

TABLE X
CENTROID EUCLIDEAN DISTANCE BETWEEN A AND H

Cl.	H ₀	H ₁	H ₂
A ₀	0.0000	3.2082	4.7545
A ₁	4.6557	1.5174	0.1073
A ₂	3.1561	0.0643	1.6746

TABLE XI
CORRELATION BETWEEN A AND H

Cl.	H ₀	H ₁	H ₂
A ₀	1.0000	0.7623	0.6166
A ₁	0.6227	0.9809	0.9999
A ₂	0.7695	0.9999	0.9770

B. Repeated Bisection (A) vs. Direct (B)

1) Results on Portuguese Dataset

A₀ - A₇ are clusters given by Repeated Bisection and B₀ - B₇ are clusters given by Direct algorithms. The Sim(A, B) is 0.7813.

TABLE XII
SIMILARITY MATRIX BETWEEN A AND B

Cl.	B ₀	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅	B ₆	B ₇
A ₀	0.8303	0.0004	0.0000	0.0005	0.0058	0.0605	0.0074	0.0000
A ₁	0.0032	0.8965	0.0004	0.0000	0.0009	0.0144	0.0038	0.0000
A ₂	0.0029	0.0030	0.0081	0.5000	0.0219	0.0187	0.0315	0.0110
A ₃	0.0017	0.0000	0.9402	0.0000	0.0051	0.0031	0.0062	0.0004
A ₄	0.0012	0.0000	0.0008	0.0009	0.5139	0.0148	0.2877	0.0004
A ₅	0.0045	0.0014	0.0022	0.0243	0.0806	0.5542	0.0469	0.0056
A ₆	0.0151	0.0342	0.0057	0.2234	0.0018	0.0345	0.0969	0.0596
A ₇	0.0004	0.0004	0.0009	0.0022	0.0059	0.0072	0.0250	0.8179

2) Results on Iris Dataset

Clusters A₀ - A₂ are clusters given by Repeated Bisection and B₀ - B₂ are clusters given by Direct clustering algorithm. The similarity between Repeated Bisection and Direct is 1, suggesting 100% similarity between the clusters given by A and B, which infers that Repeated Bisection and Direct algorithms gave clusters with 100% similarity.

TABLE XIII
SIMILARITY MATRIX BETWEEN A AND B

Cl.	B ₁		B ₂		B ₁		B ₂	
	----Fractional values----		----Decimal Values----		----Fractional values----		----Decimal Values----	
A ₀	50/50	0/105	0/95	1.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
A ₁	0/105	55/55	0/100	0.0000	1.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
A ₂	0/95	0/100	45/45	0.0000	0.0000	1.0000	0.0000	0.0000

The comparison of the results of the Repeated Bisection and Direct clustering algorithms showed perfect matches with each other once again supporting our 95% similarity comparison result.

TABLE XIV
 CENTROID EUCLIDEAN DISTANCE BETWEEN A AND B

Cl.	B ₀	B ₁	B ₂
A ₀	0.0000	4.6557	3.1561
A ₁	4.6557	0.0000	1.5721
A ₂	3.1561	1.5721	0.0000

TABLE XV
 PEARSON CORRELATION BETWEEN A AND B

Cl.	B ₀	B ₁	B ₂
A ₀	1.0000	0.6227	0.7695
A ₁	0.6227	1.0000	0.9786
A ₂	0.7695	0.9786	1.0000

C. Repeated Bisection (A) vs. Agglomerative (C)

1) Results on Portuguese Dataset

A₀ - A₇ are clusters given by the Repeated Bisection and C₀ - C₇ are clusters given by Agglomerative algorithm. The Sim(A, C) is 0.6078.

TABLE XVI
 SIMILARITY MATRIX BETWEEN A AND C

Cl.	C ₀	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆	C ₇
A ₀	0.0376	0.0057	0.0348	0.4578	0.1046	0.0115	0.0291	0.0263
A ₁	0.5085	0.0037	0.0155	0.0353	0.0197	0.0143	0.0572	0.0231
A ₂	0.0111	0.0122	0.0372	0.0130	0.1867	0.0330	0.0786	0.0343
A ₃	0.0366	0.6403	0.0253	0.0058	0.0169	0.0218	0.0211	0.0337
A ₄	0.0091	0.0111	0.3647	0.0246	0.0735	0.0196	0.0740	0.0347
A ₅	0.0321	0.0086	0.1704	0.0298	0.1365	0.0142	0.0715	0.0744
A ₆	0.0203	0.0053	0.0330	0.0201	0.0372	0.0256	0.0449	0.2781
A ₇	0.0226	0.0102	0.0313	0.0114	0.0223	0.3342	0.1618	0.0641

2) Results on Iris Dataset

Clusters A₀ - A₂ are clusters given by Repeated Bisection and C₀ - C₂ are clusters given by Agglomerative clustering algorithm. The Sim(A, C) is 0.9360. Observe that clusters A₀ and C₀ are 100% similar; however clusters A₁ and C₁, and A₂ and C₂ are 87% and 86% similar respectively, which brought the average similarity down to 93% compared to Repeated Bisection and Direct.

TABLE XVII
 SIMILARITY MATRIX BETWEEN A AND C

Cl.	C ₀	C ₁	C ₂	C ₀	C ₁	C ₂
A ₀	50/50	0/98	0/102	1.0000	0.0000	0.0000
A ₁	0/105	48/55	7/100	0.0000	0.8727	0.0700
A ₂	0/95	0/93	45/52	0.0000	0.0000	0.8653

The comparison of the results of the Repeated Bisection and Agglomerative clustering algorithm showed near perfect matches with each other supporting our 94% similarity comparison result.

TABLE XVIII
 CENTROID EUCLIDEAN DISTANCE BETWEEN A AND C

Cl.	C ₀	C ₁	C ₂
A ₀	0.0000	4.7460	3.2698
A ₁	4.6557	0.0946	1.4382
A ₂	3.1561	1.6562	0.1407

TABLE XIX
 PEARSON CORRELATION BETWEEN A AND C

Cl.	C ₀	C ₁	C ₂
A ₀	1.0000	0.6110	0.7616
A ₁	0.6227	0.9998	0.9812
A ₂	0.7695	0.9755	0.9998

D. Repeated Bisection (A) vs. Graph (D)

1) Results on Portuguese Dataset

A₀ - A₇ are clusters given by Repeated Bisection algorithm and D₀ - D₇ are clusters given by Graph algorithm. The Sim(A, D) is 0.5963.

TABLE XX
 SIMILARITY MATRIX BETWEEN A AND D

Cl.	D ₀	D ₁	D ₂	D ₃	D ₄	D ₅	D ₆	D ₇
A ₀	0.0182	0.0022	0.0151	0.0819	0.0437	0.4552	0.0121	0.0385
A ₁	0.0297	0.0358	0.0069	0.5432	0.0160	0.0157	0.0056	0.0208
A ₂	0.0240	0.0094	0.0263	0.0229	0.0325	0.0188	0.0088	0.1887
A ₃	0.0099	0.0535	0.0160	0.0119	0.0156	0.0087	0.6552	0.0102
A ₄	0.0325	0.0069	0.1788	0.0048	0.0270	0.0648	0.0211	0.2567
A ₅	0.0276	0.0090	0.0077	0.0165	0.2869	0.0588	0.0175	0.1499
A ₆	0.2042	0.0101	0.1659	0.0175	0.0711	0.0129	0.0063	0.0274
A ₇	0.0674	0.3143	0.0637	0.0352	0.0299	0.0168	0.0348	0.0703

2) Results on Iris Dataset

Clusters A₀ - A₂ are clusters given by Repeated Bisection and D₀ - D₃ are clusters given by Graph clustering algorithms. The Sim(A, D) is 0.7425. Notice that Graph algorithm suggested 4 clusters instead of requested 3; which significantly brought the overall similarity to 74% though there are two cluster sets that are as high as 100% similar.

TABLE XXI
 SIMILARITY MATRIX BETWEEN A AND D

Cl.	D ₀	D ₁	D ₂	D ₃
A ₀	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	1.0000
A ₁	0.3454	0.6363	0.0100	0.0000
A ₂	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.9782

The comparison of the results of the Repeated Bisection and Graph clustering algorithm showed differences with each other supporting our lower 72% similarity comparison result.

TABLE XXII
 CENTROID EUCLIDEAN DISTANCE BETWEEN A AND D

Cl.	D ₀	D ₁	D ₂
A ₀	4.9639	4.4668	3.2108
A ₁	0.4564	0.2868	1.5085
A ₂	1.8694	1.4103	0.0694

TABLE XXIII
 PEARSON CORRELATION BETWEEN A AND D

Cl.	D ₀	D ₁	D ₂
A ₀	0.6044	0.6318	0.7674
A ₁	0.9996	0.9998	0.9793
A ₂	0.9731	0.9811	0.9999

E. Repeated Bisection (A) vs. K-means (E)

The comparison of the results of the Repeated Bisection and K-means clustering algorithm showed significant difference with each other once again supporting our 67% similarity

comparison result.

TABLE XXIV
 CENTROID EUCLIDEAN DISTANCE BETWEEN A AND E

Cl.	E ₀	E ₁	E ₂
A ₀	0.6700	4.0561	0.2635
A ₁	4.4354	0.6187	4.5921
A ₂	2.8878	0.9544	3.1245

TABLE XXV
 PEARSON CORRELATION BETWEEN A AND E

Cl.	E ₀	E ₁	E ₂
A ₀	0.9902	0.6858	0.9997
A ₁	0.7238	0.9964	0.6074
A ₂	0.8499	0.9924	0.7567

F. Repeated Bisection (A) vs. K-medoids (F)

The comparison of the results of the Repeated Bisection and K-medoids clustering algorithm showed significant difference with each other once again supporting our 66% similarity comparison result.

TABLE XXVI
 CENTROID EUCLIDEAN DISTANCE BETWEEN A AND F

Cl.	F ₀	F ₁	F ₂
A ₀	0.3340	4.0372	0.5154
A ₁	4.6003	0.6400	4.5303
A ₂	3.1419	0.9325	2.9908

TABLE XXVII
 PEARSON CORRELATION BETWEEN A AND F

Cl.	F ₀	F ₁	F ₂
A ₀	0.9996	0.6862	0.9956
A ₁	0.6016	0.9964	0.6925
A ₂	0.7520	0.9924	0.8255

G. Repeated Bisection (A) vs. EM (G)

The comparison of the results of the Repeated Bisection and EM clustering algorithm showed significant difference with each supporting the 84% similarity comparison result, as it was not quite as bad as K-means, nor as good as algorithms A, B, or C.

TABLE XXVIII
 CENTROID EUCLIDEAN DISTANCE BETWEEN A AND G

Cl.	G ₀	G ₁	G ₂
A ₀	3.3668	4.9992	0.0000
A ₁	1.3707	0.4098	4.6557
A ₂	0.2328	1.9494	3.1561

TABLE XXIX
 PEARSON CORRELATION BETWEEN A AND G

Cl.	G ₀	G ₁	G ₂
A ₀	0.7365	0.6174	1.0000
A ₁	0.9878	0.9999	0.6227
A ₂	0.9986	0.9773	0.7695

VI. CONCLUSION

The similarity measure that we proposed has experimentally demonstrated consistently similar results to popular measures of Euclidian distance (between cluster centroids) and Pearson

correlation. The measure provides the benefit of allowing the aggregated comparison between differing algorithms to allow users to identify the best available clustering algorithm for their applications. Our results show that Repeated Bisection and Direct hierarchical clustering algorithms consistently produced clusters that are most similar to expert labeled categories for both smaller data sets with fewer features (Iris) and large dataset (translated Portuguese-English corpus) with a much larger number of features. Though there remains much room for additional research, our preliminary results indicate that Repeated Bisection and Direct algorithms can be used for clustering both small and large scale datasets, for example, foreign language text document clustering.

With the intriguing initial results, our future work will include expansion and verification of the proposed algorithm through the use of larger datasets along with various feature sizes, sample sizes, and expansion with the numbers of categories to work with.

The techniques can be extended to various real-world problems such as classification and clustering of malware, email analysis (finding social graph among the users based on email contents, for instance) in digital forensics. Since unsupervised clustering algorithms do not give accuracy; the proposed algorithm can be applied to find the best clustering algorithm for many real-life applications where clustering techniques are applied. The approach should enable users to experimentally compare various clustering algorithms and choose the one that best serves the problem.

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